

Pre-training using Masked Autoencoder on Event Camera Data

Emma Norrby, Tomas Wilkinson, David Gustafsson and Per Nyblom
Swedish Defence Research Agency (FOI)
Email: emma.norrby@foi.se

I. INTRODUCTION

Event cameras offer high temporal resolution, low latency, and low power consumption, but their sparse and asynchronous outputs introduce challenges for traditional computer vision models. Event cameras are highly suitable for real-time applications, but they require specialized algorithms to handle their challenging data format. The limited availability of large-scale labeled datasets further complicates event-based learning, making self-supervised learning approaches suitable as they can leverage unlabeled data to learn useful visual representations. Masked Autoencoders (MAE), adapted for conventional video data, have shown strong performance by learning spatiotemporal features through self-supervised reconstruction, and have demonstrated improvements in both accuracy and training efficiency compared to supervised approaches.

II. METHODOLOGY

This work investigates [1] whether Masked Autoencoders as Spatiotemporal Learners (spatiotemporal MAE) [2] can be effectively adapted for event camera data.

Two event data representations are used, the Compact Spatio-Temporal Representation (CSTR) [3] and the Event Histogram. The CSTR includes the mean timestamps of positive and negative events, as well as the histogram (event count), in a three-channel image-like format. The Event Histogram includes the histograms of the negative and positive events separately. The representations are evaluated across the event datasets DailyDVS-200, N-Cars, and THU-EACT-50-CHL.

The impact of different Vision Transformer (ViT) model sizes and temporal resolutions (1, 2, 4, and 8 frames) is investigated. Two masking strategies, random masking and sparsity-aware masking, are also evaluated. Random masking removes patches randomly, and sparsity-aware masking weights the masking to increase the probability of masking patches that contain no or few events.

Due to the variation in dataset sizes, transfer learning is also explored to potentially further improve performance on downstream tasks. In this setup, pre-training is performed on one dataset, followed by finetuning with labels on a different dataset.

III. RESULTS

Pre-training with spatiotemporal MAE improves classification accuracy and reduces training time compared to training from scratch. On Daily-DVS-200 pre-training with ViT-Small and 8 frames, accuracy improves from 21.3 % (trained from scratch) to 47.7% where training from scratch takes 3 times longer to train. CSTR generally yields higher classification accuracy, while the Event Histogram achieves lower reconstruction error.

Random masking is effective across configurations, while sparsity-aware masking shows marginal benefits with the histogram representation but does not improve performance with CSTR. Higher temporal resolution and larger model sizes contribute to improved accuracy but require increased computational resources.

Transfer learning from DailyDVS-200 to THU-EACT-50-CHL achieves an accuracy of 67.7%, surpassing the previously best reported result of 58.5%. These findings suggest that spatiotemporal masked autoencoders are a promising approach for self-supervised learning in event-based vision, particularly when transfer learning is used to leverage larger datasets. A summary of the results can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I
BEST CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY ACROSS DATASETS AND SETTINGS USING ViT-SMALL. PRE-TRAINING DONE ON DAILYDVS-200.

Dataset	MAE Pre-training	Acc(%)	Frames
DailyDVS-200	✗	21.3	8
DailyDVS-200	✓	47.7	8
N-Cars	✗	90.3	2
N-Cars	✓	92.9	1
THU ^{EACT} -50-CHL	✗	25.9	2
THU ^{EACT} -50-CHL	✓	67.7	8

REFERENCES

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